

Dyes Derived from Acenaphthenequinone. Part V. 2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene- indigos.

BY SISIR KUMAR GUHA.

Martinet (*Rev. Gen. Mat. Col.*, 1921, **25**, 17)* has formulated a rule that the effect of the two auxochromes in *para* position (5:5') is cumulative and when in *meta* position (6:6') with respect to one another they act in contrary direction. This rule is particularly well exemplified in the indigoid series. It has been found that all 5:5' derivatives are decidedly deeper in colour than the corresponding 6:6' derivatives. The substituents may be C_2H_5S , C_2H_5O , Halogen, CH_3 , NH_2 , OH etc. (*cf.* Rowe, "Colour Index," 1924 Ed., Nos. 1216, 1217, 1209, 1210, 1208, 1182, 1248, 1193; Auwers and Arndt, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 541; D.R.P. 204763, Friedlander, 9, 589; G. P. 239673, 240805, Viles, *J.S.D.C.*, 1914, **30**, 25, etc.).

In the present investigation, indigoid dyes have been obtained from acenaphthenequinone, 3-chloro-, 3-bromo-, and its 1-methoxy derivative and 6-methyl-3-hydroxy-thionaphthene (Friedlander, *loc. cit.*; Auwers and Thies, *Ber.*, 1920, **53**, 2293) with the object of studying the effect, if any, produced on the colour of 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigo, commercially known as Ciba scarlet-G (Bezdzik and Friedlander, *Monatsh.*, 1908, **29**, 386; E.P. 344/08, G.P. 205377) and its various derivatives (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 423) by the introduction of CH_3 group in the 6-position of the thionaphthene nucleus and how far this effect can be compared with 2-(5-methyl) thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigos (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 679) and thus to see if the rule of Martinet is applicable to 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos as far as one methyl group in the thionaphthene part of the molecule is concerned.

The indigoid dyes described here are all sparingly soluble in alcohol and all of them dissolve in strong sulphuric acid giving deep green solutions from which the substances are reprecipitated by the addition of water in the form of flocculent precipitate, suitable for dyeing on

* The paper is available to me in the form of an abstract only (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **4**, 273).

wool from an acid bath. When strongly heated above the melting points, the dyes behave similarly to the corresponding 5-methyl derivatives (Guha, *loc. cit.*). The parent substance, its chloro- and bromo- derivatives are reduced by alkaline hydrosulphite giving violet blue, and blue vat from which dyes are regenerated on cotton by air. But the methoxy derivatives offered considerable resistance to reduction; after prolonged treatment, the faint violet vat obtained in this case, turned by atmospheric oxygen into faint pink only [*cf.* 2-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-acenaphthylene-indigo and its 5-methyl derivative, Staudinger, Goldstein and Schlenker, *Helv., Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 342; Guha, *loc. cit.*].

All these indigoid dyes are distinctly lighter in colour than those of the corresponding 5-methyl compounds (Guha, *loc. cit.*). A comparison of the colours of the dyeing on wool and on cotton of the compounds mentioned here with those obtained from the corresponding 5-methyl derivatives is given below. The substances are arranged, in both the series, according to the gradual increase of the shades of dyes developed on cloth and on wool.

Name of the compounds.	Dyeing shades	
	on wool.	on cotton.
2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigo ...	Vermillion	Vermillion
2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigo ...	Scarlet red	Scarlet red
2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro)-acenaphthylene indigo ...	Vermillion	Vermillion
2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro)-acenaphthylene indigo ...	Bright scarlet red	Deep scarlet red
2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-acenaphthylene indigo ...	Bright vermilion	Light red
2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-acenaphthylene indigo ...	Deep scarlet red	Deep scarlet red
2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-acenaphthylene indigo ...	Deep red	Faint pink
2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-acenaphthylene indigo ...	Deep red	Pink

Further studies in 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos having CH₃ group in 4-position of the thionaphthene nucleus are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigo.

The solutions of acenaphthenequinone (0.455 g.) in boiling glacial acetic acid (80 c.c.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.41 g.) in boiling glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) were treated with strong hydrochloric acid (6 c.c.) and shaken when vermilion coloured needle shaped voluminous crystalline precipitate immediately separated out. The mixture was heated to boiling for 15 minutes and filtered hot, washed with acetic acid and hot water. It was purified by boiling with alcohol and finally crystallised from glacial acetic acid or xylene in clusters of needles, m.p. 305°. The dye is soluble in chloroform, amyl alcohol, benzene, xylene, nitrobenzene, aniline, pyridine; difficultly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, glacial acetic acid; sparingly soluble in acetone and alcohol. It dyes cotton in vermilion shade from a deep violet blue (almost blue) vat obtained by the action of alkaline hydrosulphite and wool in the same colour from an acid bath. (Found: S, 9.38. $C_{21}H_{12}O_2S$ requires S, 9.75 per cent).

2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro)-acenaphthylene-indigo.—3-Chloroacenaphthenequinone (0.866 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.656 g.) in hot glacial acetic acid (95 c.c.) were treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.). The condensation product crystallised in fibre-like vermilion needles which were purified as the preceding compound and crystallised from pyridine or xylene in clusters of needles, m.p. 297°. It dyes wool in vermilion shade from an acid bath and cotton in the same shade from the blue vat obtained by alkaline hydrosulphite. It is difficultly soluble in benzene and amyl alcohol and the other properties resemble those of the preceding compound. (Found: Cl, 9.59. $C_{21}H_{11}O_2ClS$ requires Cl, 9.79 per cent).

2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-acenaphthylene-indigo was obtained in the same way as the two foregoing compounds by the

condensation of 3-bromoacenaphthenequinone (1.044 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.656 g.) in presence of 105 c.c. of hot glacial acetic acid and 3 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The silky, bright, vermilion coloured crystalline product, after being boiled with alcohol, was crystallised from xylene in fine long rectangles, m.p. 302°. It dyes wool in bright vermilion shade from an acid bath and it dyes cotton in light red shade from the blue vat, formed by the action of alkaline hydrosulphite, although not so readily obtained as in the case of the mother compound and its chloro derivative. It resembles the chloro compound in its other properties. (Found : Br, 19.34. $C_{21}H_{11}O_2BrS$ requires Br, 19.65 per cent).

2- (6-Methyl) - thionaphthene - 8' - (1'-methoxy) - acenaphthylene-indigo.—The deep brownish red hot solution of β -methoxyacenaphthenequinone (0.636 g.) and the methylhydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in 115 c.c. of glacial acetic acid on treatment with 10 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid immediately turned deep violet red (almost black) which on shaking deposited at once scarlet red sharp needle-shaped crystals. The whole of the mixture was boiled for 30 minutes, filtered hot, washed with acetic acid and hot water. It was found difficult to purify the substance by heating successively with alcohol and acetic acid to remove minute traces of the unreacted diketone. It was crystallised from pyridine, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and hot water. It melts at 300° (softening at 298°). It dyes wool in deep red shades from an acid bath and cotton in faint pink colour from an alkaline hydrosulphite faint violet vat. It resembles the mother compound in this series in solubility. (Found : S, 9.1. $C_{22}H_{14}O_3S$ requires S, 8.93 per cent).